

Ion-exchange Equilibrium Studies with some Weak Acid-Strong Base Salts

D. J. Patel, R. A. Bhatt, and S. L. Bafna

Ion-exchange equilibria of some weak acid-strong base salts with styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer-based sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins of different relative degree of cross-linking have been studied.

Ion exchange equilibrium studies of some strong acid—strong base salts with styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer-based sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins of different relative degree of cross-linking (% nominal divinylbenzene content) have already been reported¹. This work is concerned with similar studies with some weak acid-strong base salts.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resins were from the samples used in the earlier work¹. The chemicals were of A.R. (B.D.H.) or C.P. grade. The solutions were prepared in distilled water. Sodium acetate was made anhydrous and then a known weight was dissolved in a known volume of water. For other salts, standard solutions of acid and base containing equivalent quantities were mixed. The solutions were suitably diluted. The procedure for ion exchange equilibrium studies was similar to that reported earlier¹.

NOMENCLATURE

- $[\bar{H}^+]_i$ = the g. equivalents of resin in hydrogen form added initially per litre of solution.
 $[M^+]_i$ = the initial concentration of cations M^+ in aqueous solution in g. equivalents per litre.
 $[AH]_e$ = the concentration of titratable acid in g. equivalents per litre at equilibrium.
P.E. = percent exchange of the maximum possible =

$$100 \frac{[AH]_e}{[M^+]_i} \text{ or } 100 \frac{[AH]_e}{[H]_i} \text{ whichever}$$

is higher and

$$R = \frac{[\bar{H}^+]_i}{[M^+]_i}$$

DISCUSSION

The exchange equilibria were studied for resins X1, X2, X4, X8, X12, X16, and IR-200 with sodium formate, sodium acetate, sodium oxalate, potassium oxalate, sodium citrate, and potassium citrate. Table I records some of the results to illustrate the type of data obtained.

When a cation-exchange resin is placed in an aqueous solution of weak monobasic acid-strong base salt, MA, the following equilibria exist.

and for salts of polybasic acids, the number of equilibria in (2) to be considered are equal to the basicity of the acid. Hence when AH is a weak acid, $[\bar{M}^+]_0$ is relatively much greater than $[H^+]_0$ and this is more so, the higher the pK value/values of the weak acid. Hence the value of P.E. at a particular value of R is much higher than it would be if the salt were strong acid-strong base type under similar conditions. That it is so is illustrated by the data recorded in Table I. The value of P.E. is high and reaches almost 100% for lower and higher values of R. This is of interest in that for the conversion of a resin to a particular cation form, the use of weak acid—strong base salts may need a smaller volume of solution and hence a faster complete conversion may be achieved. It is, however, to be seen that molecular sorption⁶ of the weak acid on the resin should be low, so as to facilitate its elimination in the usual washing of the resin in the particular cation form. It was also noted that the effect of the degree of cross-linking as well as cation (Na^+ or K^+) on the value of P.E. (which is high) was not marked.

TABLE I

Salt.	$10^3[\bar{H}^+]_i$	$10^3[\bar{M}^+]_0$	P.E.
Sodium formate	2.264	2.248	99.2
$10^3[M^+]_i=3.985$	3.753	3.564	89.5
	5.243	3.689	92.5
	7.570	3.633	96.1
	10.47	3.862	96.9
Sodium acetate	2.305	2.305	100.0
$10^3[M^+]_i=4.000$	3.766	3.619	96.1
	5.217	3.894	97.3
	6.751	3.938	98.4
	9.080	3.967	99.1
Sodium oxalate	1.864	1.800	96.5
$10^3[M^+]_i=3.985$	2.226	2.087	93.7
	5.234	3.124	78.4
	7.475	3.425	85.9
	10.45	3.600	90.3
Sodium citrate	2.236	2.226	99.5
$10^3[M^+]_i=4.000$	3.735	3.376	90.4
	5.170	3.787	94.6
	7.490	3.848	96.2
	10.46	3.945	98.6

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODAS

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